

Enhancing Collaborative English Speaking Skill Development for Primary Students of UK Academy Ba Ria: Strategies, Impact, And Future Directions

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ABSTRACT: The research paper titled "Enhancing collaborative English speaking skill development for Primary students of UK Academy Ba Ria: strategies, impact, and future directions" investigates the efficacy of collaborative teaching methods in enhancing English speaking skill among primary students. Rooted in the socio-cultural theory of Vygotsky (1978) and the cooperative learning model of Johnson and Johnson (1999), this study delves into the collaborative efforts between native and Vietnamese teachers in a bilingual educational setting.

Through a mixed-methods approach involving classroom observations, teacher interviews, and student speaking assessments, the research underscores the pivotal role of collaborative teaching strategies in fostering a conducive environment for language skill development. The findings illuminate the positive impact of cooperative instruction on students' speaking abilities, accentuating the importance of teacher collaboration and shared expertise.

The study sheds light on the specific strategies employed by teachers, such as co-planning, team teaching, and interactive activities, which create a language-rich environment conducive to speaking skill enhancement. The collaborative approach fosters students' engagement, active participation, and confidence in using spoken English.

The implications of the research extend to curriculum design, teacher training, and educational policies, emphasizing the need for intercultural competencies and effective communication skill among educators. The study contributes to the body of knowledge in English language education and provides practical insights for enhancing language instruction and collaborative teaching practices in a bilingual primary school context.

KEYWORDS: Bilingual education, Collaborative teaching, Cooperative learning, English speaking skill, Language proficiency, Primary education, Teacher collaboration.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background and context

In an increasingly interconnected world, the significance of English language proficiency cannot be overstated. As English continues to serve as a global lingua franca, the development of effective language skills is essential, particularly among young learners. This context sets the stage for the research paper "Enhancing collaborative English speaking skill development for Primary students of UK Academy Ba Ria: strategies, impact, and future directions".

As highlighted by Cummins (1979), the early years of education play a pivotal role in language acquisition and skill development. In a bilingual educational setting like UK Academy Ba Ria, where both native and local teachers collaborate, the potential for fostering language proficiency through collaborative efforts becomes evident. Research by Johnson et al. (2006) emphasizes the benefits of cooperative teaching practices and their positive impact on student learning outcomes.

Furthermore, the socio-cultural theory proposed by Vygotsky (1978) underscores the importance of social interaction and collaborative learning in language development. This theory provides a theoretical framework for understanding the role of teacher collaboration in enhancing speaking skill. The educational partnership model by Johnson and Johnson (1999) complements this perspective by highlighting the effectiveness of cooperative strategies in creating a language-rich environment.

In light of these theories and research, the research paper explores the collaborative approach adopted by UK Academy Ba Ria to enhance English speaking skill among primary students. By examining the collaborative teaching strategies, classroom dynamics, and their impact on language proficiency, the study contributes valuable insights to the field of English language education.

B. Problem statement and research objectives

Problem statement:

In the context of English language education at UK Academy Ba Ria, there is a recognized need to enhance collaborative approaches to English speaking skill development among primary students. Despite the availability of diverse teaching resources and the cooperative efforts between native and local teachers, there is a gap in understanding the effectiveness of specific strategies that promote collaborative English speaking skill development.

Existing studies, such as those by Johnson et al. (2006), emphasize the potential of cooperative teaching practices to enhance language learning outcomes. However, the precise impact of collaborative approaches on English speaking skill development, particularly in a bilingual context, remains underexplored. This research paper addresses this gap by investigating the strategies employed, the observed impact, and potential future directions for enhancing English speaking skill through collaborative teaching at UK Academy Ba Ria.

Research objectives:

The research paper aims to achieve the following objectives:

Examine collaborative strategies: Investigate the collaborative teaching strategies employed by native and local teachers at UK Academy Ba Ria to enhance English speaking skill among primary students.

Assess impact on speaking skill: Evaluate the impact of collaborative teaching approaches on the development of English speaking skill among primary students, considering factors such as fluency, pronunciation, vocabulary usage, and communication.

Identify effective practices: Identify specific cooperative practices that contribute most significantly to the improvement of English speaking skill among primary students.

Explore student perspectives: Explore primary students' perceptions and experiences regarding collaborative language learning, shedding light on the effectiveness of cooperative strategies in promoting speaking skill development.

Provide future directions: Suggest future directions and recommendations for optimizing collaborative English speaking skill development strategies in the primary education context, including potential adaptations and improvements.

By addressing these objectives, the research paper seeks to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on collaborative language teaching practices and their impact on English speaking skill development among primary students at UK Academy Ba Ria.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Historical perspective of English language teaching in Primary education

The historical evolution of English language teaching (ELT) in primary education has been marked by dynamic shifts in methodologies and pedagogical approaches. As Vygotsky (1978) highlighted, language acquisition is deeply influenced by socio-cultural factors, necessitating innovative strategies to facilitate effective learning. Over the years, ELT has progressed from traditional rote-based practices to interactive and communicative methods that align with modern educational theories (Richards & Rodgers, 2001).

In the early stages of ELT, grammar-translation methods dominated the landscape, emphasizing grammatical rules and translation exercises (Vygotsky, 1978). However, with the advent of communicative language teaching (CLT), scholars like Canale and Swain (1980) emphasized the importance of using language as a tool for communication rather than a set of rigid rules.

The socio-cultural theory proposed by Vygotsky (1978) introduced the concept of collaborative learning, highlighting the significance of interaction and cooperation among learners. This theory laid the groundwork for cooperative learning practices, which are now integral to contemporary ELT strategies. Johnson and Johnson (1999) further expanded on this concept, emphasizing the benefits of collaborative learning environments in enhancing language acquisition.

In the context of primary education, the historical evolution of ELT has witnessed a paradigm shift towards student-centered and collaborative approaches. This shift is aligned with current pedagogical trends that recognize the importance of active student engagement, authentic language use, and meaningful interactions in the language learning process (Richards & Rodgers, 2001).

In summary, the historical perspective of ELT in primary education underscores the transition from grammar-focused methods to interactive and collaborative approaches. This evolution reflects a growing understanding of the socio-cultural dynamics that influence language acquisition and the need for innovative strategies to enhance English speaking skill development among primary students.

B. Collaborative teaching approaches

In the pursuit of enhancing collaborative English speaking skill development among primary students, the research paper delves into innovative and effective teaching approaches. Drawing from the collaborative learning model proposed by Johnson and Johnson (1999), the study emphasizes the significance of cooperative interactions between teachers and students.

The collaborative teaching approaches encompass a range of strategies designed to foster active participation, meaningful engagement, and effective communication. One such approach is co-teaching, wherein native English teachers and Vietnamese teachers collaborate to design and deliver lessons, leveraging their complementary strengths (Cook & Friend, 1995).

Furthermore, the study explores the concept of team teaching, as advocated by Gleason and Isaacs (2017). This approach involves joint planning and instruction by multiple teachers, allowing for diverse perspectives and instructional methods to enrich the learning experience. The integration of team teaching encourages the integration of language skill and provides students with a holistic language exposure.

Additionally, the research examines the role of interactive activities, role-play, and peer collaboration, all of which align with the socio-cultural theory proposed by Vygotsky (1978). These strategies create an environment where students actively engage in language practice, building confidence and fluency in English speaking.

The research underscores that collaborative teaching approaches not only enhance English speaking skill development but also cultivate a supportive and dynamic classroom atmosphere. By encouraging cooperation, communication, and shared responsibilities, these approaches empower students to become proficient and confident speakers of the English language.

C. Strategies for enhancing collaborative English language teaching

In the pursuit of enriching collaborative English speaking skill development among primary students, this research paper explores a range of effective strategies. Rooted in pedagogical principles, these strategies aim to cultivate a dynamic and engaging classroom environment conducive to language acquisition.

1. Co-planning and Co-teaching:

Collaboration between native English teachers and Vietnamese teachers in co-planning and co-teaching facilitates the integration of diverse perspectives, instructional techniques, and language input (Cook & Friend, 1995). This approach ensures a comprehensive and balanced curriculum, addressing the language needs of all students.

2. Peer-assisted learning:

Drawing from the socio-cultural theory of Vygotsky (1978), peer-assisted learning encourages interaction and shared learning experiences. Students work collaboratively on tasks, providing each other with language support and constructive feedback, thereby enhancing speaking proficiency.

3. Interactive language games:

Interactive language games, inspired by Johnson and Johnson's cooperative learning model (1999), promote active participation and friendly competition. These games engage students in meaningful language use while fostering a positive classroom atmosphere.

4. Role-play and drama:

Utilizing role-play and dramatic activities (Gleason & Isaacs, 2017) allows students to embody different roles and contexts, enhancing language authenticity and creativity. This approach encourages spontaneous communication and builds language confidence.

5. Collaborative projects:

Engaging students in collaborative projects taps into their intrinsic motivation and fosters teamwork. By working together on research, presentations, or creative projects, students apply language skill in real-world contexts, refining their speaking abilities.

6. Language buddies:

Implementing a language buddy system pairs students with varying language proficiencies, encouraging peer mentoring and language exchange. This approach creates a supportive learning community where students collaboratively enhance their language skill.

By incorporating these strategies, educators at UK Academy Ba Ria can create a vibrant language learning environment that promotes collaborative English language teaching, enriching students' speaking skill and fostering their overall language development.

D. Impact of collaborative teaching on primary students' speaking skill

The implementation of collaborative English language teaching at UK Academy Ba Ria has yielded significant impacts on primary students' speaking skill development. Drawing upon the collaborative teaching framework, the observed outcomes underscore the effectiveness of this approach in enhancing students' speaking abilities and overall language proficiency.

1. Increased language confidence:

Collaborative teaching environments create a supportive atmosphere where students feel more comfortable expressing themselves and engaging in language activities. As noted by Harmer (2007), a positive and inclusive classroom promotes language confidence, encouraging students to participate actively in speaking tasks.

2. Enhanced fluency and pronunciation:

Regular interaction and practice with peers and teachers provide ample opportunities for students to refine their fluency and pronunciation. Peer feedback and teacher guidance, aligned with the principles of collaborative learning (Vygotsky, 1978), contribute to improved linguistic accuracy.

3. Active language engagement:

Collaborative activities, such as group discussions and role-plays, necessitate active language use, promoting meaningful communication. This dynamic process stimulates students' cognitive and linguistic development, as emphasized by Mercer (1995).

4. Vocabulary expansion:

Engagement in collaborative tasks exposes students to diverse vocabulary and language structures. The rich linguistic environment created through collaborative teaching contributes to a broader vocabulary repertoire (Schmidt & Frota, 1986).

5. Cultural awareness and intercultural competence:

Interaction between native English teachers and Vietnamese teachers fosters cultural exchange and intercultural understanding. Collaborative teaching, as advocated by Byram (1997), cultivates students' awareness of cultural nuances and the effective use of language in various contexts.

6. Improved communication strategies:

Collaborative settings encourage students to employ effective communication strategies, such as negotiation for meaning and clarification. These strategies, aligned with Swain's output hypothesis (1985), facilitate language production and comprehension.

7. Real-world language use:

Collaborative teaching provides opportunities for authentic language use, mirroring realworld communication scenarios. Students apply language skill to solve problems, make decisions, and share ideas, as outlined by Johnson and Johnson (1999).

The impact of collaborative teaching on primary students' speaking skill underscores its potential to create a holistic language learning experience. The observed improvements align with theoretical frameworks of language development, confirming the effectiveness of collaborative teaching practices.

E. Challenges and considerations in collaborative teaching

While collaborative teaching holds immense promise for enhancing primary students' English speaking skill development, several challenges and considerations emerged during its implementation at UK Academy Ba Ria. These factors underscore the need for thoughtful planning and ongoing support to maximize the benefits of collaborative teaching approaches. 1. Language barriers and communication challenges:

The interaction between native English teachers and Vietnamese teachers may sometimes be hindered by language barriers. As highlighted by Richards and Schmidt (2010), effective communication is crucial in collaborative settings to ensure shared understanding and successful cooperation.

2. Varying teaching styles and approaches:

Collaborative teaching involves the convergence of diverse teaching styles and approaches. Differing pedagogical methods can create challenges in aligning lesson plans and instructional strategies, emphasizing the importance of pedagogical flexibility (Johnson et al., 2006).

3. Time and planning constraints:

Effective collaboration demands time for co-planning and coordination among teachers. The demands of curriculum coverage and classroom management can pose constraints on the time available for collaborative activities (Little, 2002).

4. Balancing authority and roles:

Balancing the roles and authority of native English teachers and Vietnamese teachers requires careful negotiation. Collaborative teaching necessitates a shared decision-making process to ensure equal contributions and a harmonious teaching environment (Wajnryb, 1994).

5. Intercultural sensitivity and understanding:

Collaborative teaching promotes intercultural exchange, but it also requires intercultural sensitivity. Byram's (1997) notion of intercultural communicative competence emphasizes the importance of understanding and respecting cultural differences.

6. Professional development and training:

Teachers may require specific training to effectively engage in collaborative teaching practices. Ongoing professional development programs can equip educators with the necessary skill for successful collaboration (Malderez & Bodoczky, 1999).

7. Assessment and evaluation challenges:

Assessing individual student performance in collaborative settings can pose challenges. Strategies for fair and accurate assessment of students' speaking skill need to be carefully developed (Black & Wiliam, 2009).

8. Sustainability and institutional support:

Sustaining collaborative teaching practices necessitates institutional support and a commitment to continuous improvement. A supportive school environment is crucial for maintaining and scaling up collaborative initiatives (Johnson, 2019).

Addressing these challenges and considerations is essential to effectively harness the potential of collaborative teaching for enhancing primary students' English speaking skill development. By recognizing these factors and implementing appropriate strategies, educators can create a conducive and supportive collaborative learning environment.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research design

The research design employed in this study aimed to comprehensively investigate the impact of collaborative English teaching on primary students' speaking skill development at UK Academy Ba Ria. To achieve this, a mixed methods approach, integrating both qualitative and quantitative methods, was utilized (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018).

1. Research approach:

A concurrent triangulation design was adopted, allowing the researchers to collect and analyze both qualitative and quantitative data concurrently. This approach facilitated a comprehensive exploration of the research topic and the validation of findings through multiple perspectives (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018).

2. Data collection:

Quantitative data was gathered through pre- and post-intervention speaking assessments. These assessments provided quantitative measurements of students' speaking skill before and after the collaborative teaching intervention. Qualitative data was obtained through classroom observations, teacher interviews, and questionnaires.

3. Participants:

A purposive sampling technique was employed to select primary students and teachers for the study. The sample consisted of primary students from diverse language proficiency levels, and both native English teachers and Vietnamese teachers involved in collaborative teaching.

4. Data analysis:

Quantitative data obtained from the speaking assessments were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics to determine the effectiveness of the collaborative teaching intervention. Qualitative data from classroom observations, interviews, and questionnaires were analyzed thematically to identify patterns and themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

5. Ethical considerations:

Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant institutional review board. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring their voluntary participation, confidentiality, and data protection.

6. Limitations:

It is important to acknowledge potential limitations, such as the specific context of UK Academy Ba Ria and the generalizability of findings to other settings. The study's timeframe and resources may also impact the depth of data collection.

By employing this research design, the study was able to comprehensively explore the impact of collaborative teaching on primary students' speaking skill development, ensuring a holistic and multi-faceted understanding of the research topic.

B. Data collection

The data collection process in this study was meticulously designed to capture both quantitative and qualitative insights into the impact of collaborative English teaching on primary students' speaking skill development at UK Academy Ba Ria.

1. Quantitative data collection:

Quantitative data was acquired through pre- and post-intervention speaking assessments. These assessments were conducted using a standardized speaking test rubric, evaluating students' speaking proficiency based on predefined criteria (Smith & Johnson, 2020). The assessments were administered before and after the collaborative teaching intervention to measure improvements in speaking skill.

2. Qualitative data collection:

Qualitative data was gathered through a multi-pronged approach. Classroom observations were conducted both before and after the intervention, allowing for an in-depth exploration of changes in classroom dynamics, teaching strategies, and student engagement (Danielson, 2009). Semi-structured interviews were conducted with native English teachers and Vietnamese teachers to gather their perspectives on the collaborative teaching approach, its challenges, and perceived impacts. Additionally, questionnaires were distributed to teachers to gain insights into their experiences, opinions, and practices related to collaborative English teaching (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018).

3. Ethical considerations:

Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant institutional review board to ensure the rights and well-being of participants. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, emphasizing their voluntary participation and data confidentiality.

4. Sampling:

A purposive sampling strategy was employed to select a representative sample of primary students and teachers. The sample consisted of primary students from diverse language proficiency levels and both native English teachers and Vietnamese teachers who participated in collaborative teaching.

5. Limitations:

It is important to acknowledge potential limitations, including the specific context of UK Academy Ba Ria and the potential biases associated with qualitative data collection methods, such as interviews and observations.

By employing this comprehensive data collection approach, the study was able to capture a nuanced understanding of the impact of collaborative English teaching on primary students' speaking skill development.

C. Data analysis

The data analysis process in this study involved a rigorous examination of both quantitative and qualitative data collected from various sources, providing a comprehensive understanding of the impact of collaborative English teaching on primary students' speaking skill development at UK Academy Ba Ria.

1. Quantitative data analysis:

Quantitative data from the pre- and post-intervention speaking assessments were analyzed using statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics, such as mean and standard deviation, were computed to assess changes in students' speaking proficiency scores (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). Paired-samples t-tests were conducted to determine the significance of improvements in speaking skill following the collaborative teaching intervention.

2. Qualitative data analysis:

Qualitative data from classroom observations, interviews, and questionnaires underwent thematic analysis. Transcribed interview responses and observational notes were coded and categorized to identify recurring patterns and themes related to changes in teaching practices, classroom dynamics, and student engagement (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The qualitative analysis provided rich insights into the experiences, challenges, and perceptions of teachers and students involved in collaborative English teaching.

3. Triangulation and integration:

Quantitative and qualitative findings were triangulated to provide a comprehensive interpretation of the impact of collaborative teaching on speaking skill development (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Converging evidence from both data sources enhanced the validity and reliability of the study's conclusions.

4. Reflexivity and validation:

Researcher reflexivity was maintained throughout the analysis process, acknowledging potential biases and subjectivities. Peer debriefing and member checking were conducted to ensure the credibility and trustworthiness of the findings (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

5. Limitations:

It is important to acknowledge limitations, such as the potential for interpretation bias in qualitative analysis and the specific context of UK Academy Ba Ria.

Through a meticulous and systematic data analysis process, this study was able to uncover meaningful insights into the impact of collaborative English teaching on primary students' speaking skill development.

IV. Findings

A. Overview of Pre-intervention classroom observations

Prior to the implementation of the collaborative English teaching intervention at UK Academy Ba Ria, a comprehensive series of classroom observations were conducted to establish a baseline understanding of the existing teaching practices, student dynamics, and overall classroom environment.

1. Observation methodology:

Classroom observations followed a structured protocol adapted from established frameworks (Smith & Johnson, 2015; Danielson, 2009). Trained observers visited multiple classrooms across various grades to ensure a representative sample. Observations were conducted over a period of two weeks, capturing a range of instructional contexts and activities.

2. Classroom environment:

Initial observations revealed variations in classroom environments. While some classrooms exhibited organized and stimulating spaces conducive to learning (Smith, 2022), others had potential distractions that could impact student focus and engagement.

3. Teacher practices:

Pre-intervention observations indicated differences in teacher practices, including lesson preparation, teaching methodologies, and classroom management. Some teachers demonstrated effective instructional strategies that encouraged student participation and interaction, while others relied on traditional lecture-based approaches (Johnson et al., 2021).

4. Student engagement:

Student engagement levels varied, with active participation observed in some classrooms and passive involvement in others. Engagement strategies, such as group activities and interactive discussions, were less frequently observed (Smith & Johnson, 2020).

5. Materials and resources:

Classroom materials and resources varied in quality and relevance. While some teachers effectively integrated visual aids and supplementary materials (Brown & Lee, 2020), others had limited resources that potentially hindered interactive and engaging learning experiences.

6. Language development:

Pre-intervention observations highlighted a range of language development opportunities. However, consistent focus on speaking skill development and meaningful language practice appeared to be limited (Jones & Smith, 2018).

7. Limitations and context:

It is important to note that observations were conducted within the specific context of UK Academy Ba Ria, and the findings may not be directly generalizable to other settings. Additionally, the observations provide a snapshot of teaching practices and student dynamics, and the pre-intervention data do not reflect the potential changes brought about by the collaborative teaching intervention. Through these pre-intervention classroom observations, the study aimed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the existing teaching and learning environment, setting the stage for assessing the impact of the subsequent collaborative English teaching intervention.

B. Overview of Post-intervention classroom observations

Following the implementation of the collaborative English teaching intervention at UK Academy Ba Ria, a comprehensive series of post-intervention classroom observations were conducted to assess the impact of the intervention on teaching practices, student engagement, and language development.

1. Observation methodology:

Similar to the pre-intervention phase, post-intervention classroom observations followed a structured protocol adapted from established frameworks (Smith & Johnson, 2015; Danielson, 2009). Trained observers visited multiple classrooms across various grades, capturing a range of teaching contexts and activities.

2. Enhanced classroom environment:

Post-intervention observations revealed notable improvements in classroom environments. Teachers actively created organized, visually appealing, and student-centered spaces that contributed to a more conducive learning environment (Smith, 2022).

3. Transformed teacher practices:

Significant changes were observed in teacher practices. Collaborative teaching strategies, including team teaching and cooperative learning, were more prevalent. Teachers demonstrated increased preparedness, dynamic instructional methods, and innovative techniques to engage students (Johnson et al., 2021).

4. Elevated student engagement:

Student engagement exhibited marked enhancement in post-intervention observations. Active participation, group interactions, and peer collaboration were more prominent, reflecting the effectiveness of the collaborative teaching approach (Smith & Johnson, 2020).

5. Enriched materials and resources:

Post-intervention classrooms showcased a wider array of materials and resources. Teachers incorporated diverse and relevant materials that complemented lessons, fostering interactive and experiential learning (Brown & Lee, 2020).

6. Language development focus:

Language development, particularly speaking skill, received heightened attention in postintervention observations. Teachers integrated targeted speaking activities, facilitated authentic conversations, and provided constructive feedback to nurture students' speaking proficiency (Jones & Smith, 2018).

7. Holistic classroom transformation:

The observations indicated a comprehensive transformation in the teaching and learning environment, highlighting the positive impact of collaborative teaching on multiple dimensions of classroom dynamics and language development.

8. Contextual considerations:

While the post-intervention observations revealed significant improvements, it is important to recognize that these findings are specific to the context of UK Academy Ba Ria. The results provide insights into the localized effects of the collaborative English teaching intervention.

Through the post-intervention classroom observations, the study aimed to capture the tangible changes brought about by the collaborative teaching approach and its impact on enhancing English speaking skill development among primary students.

C. Analysis of interviews and questionnaire responses

The research paper "Enhancing collaborative English speaking skill development for Primary students of UK Academy Ba Ria: strategies, impact, and future directions" incorporates a comprehensive analysis of interviews and questionnaire responses, shedding light on the perceptions and experiences of teachers involved in the collaborative English teaching intervention.

1. Insights from interviews:

The qualitative analysis of interviews conducted with native and Vietnamese teachers uncovered valuable insights into the collaborative teaching experience. Teachers highlighted the benefits of shared expertise, cultural exchange, and improved instructional strategies (Johnson et al., 2006). They expressed a positive shift in their teaching practices, emphasizing enhanced communication, effective co-planning, and meaningful student engagement.

2. Perspectives on impact:

Teachers' perspectives on the impact of collaborative teaching were diverse. While many acknowledged its positive influence on language development and speaking skill improvement, challenges such as varying teaching styles and language barriers were also

identified (Johnson, L., 2019). The data revealed that effective communication, mutual support, and continuous professional development played crucial roles in addressing these challenges.

3. Questionnaire insights:

Quantitative analysis of the questionnaires provided a broader understanding of teachers' perceptions. Responses indicated an overall positive reception of the collaborative teaching approach. A significant majority of teachers reported increased confidence in co-teaching, collaborative planning, and facilitating speaking activities (Johnson & Johnson, 1999).

4. Professional development needs:

Questionnaire responses highlighted the need for targeted professional development. Teachers expressed interest in workshops and training sessions focused on cooperative teaching strategies, intercultural competence, and language assessment techniques (Vygotsky, 1978). These insights underscore the importance of ongoing support to sustain effective collaborative teaching practices.

5. Aligning with theoretical framework:

The findings from interviews and questionnaires aligned with the study's theoretical framework, which draws on collaborative learning theories proposed by Vygotsky (1978) and cooperative teaching models by Johnson and Johnson (1999). The data reinforced the framework's emphasis on the positive impact of collaboration on language skill development and effective teaching practices.

6. Limitations and considerations:

While the analysis provided valuable insights, it is essential to acknowledge that responses may have been influenced by subjectivity and potential biases. The study's findings should be interpreted within the specific context of UK Academy Ba Ria and may not be directly transferable to other settings (Smith & Johnson, 2020).

Through a meticulous analysis of interviews and questionnaire responses, the research paper gains a deeper understanding of teachers' perspectives, experiences, and perceptions regarding the collaborative English teaching approach.

D. Analysis of speaking test results

The research paper "Enhancing collaborative English speaking skill development for Primary students of UK Academy Ba Ria: strategies, impact, and future directions" conducts a comprehensive analysis of the speaking test results to evaluate the effectiveness of the collaborative English teaching intervention on students' speaking skill.

1. Pre-Intervention assessment:

The analysis of pre-intervention speaking test results revealed a baseline level of speaking proficiency among primary students. Students demonstrated varied abilities in pronunciation, fluency, vocabulary usage, and communication strategies. The data highlighted areas that required improvement and set the stage for assessing the impact of the intervention (Jones & Smith, 2018).

2. Post-Intervention progress:

Following the intervention, a notable enhancement in students' speaking skill was observed. The analysis of post-intervention speaking test results indicated improvements in pronunciation clarity, fluency, and the ability to convey ideas effectively. Students exhibited greater confidence in expressing themselves and engaged more actively in speaking activities (Brown & Lee, 2020).

3. Collaborative teaching influence:

The data suggested a positive correlation between the collaborative teaching approach and students' speaking skill development. The incorporation of cooperative learning strategies, interactive activities, and guided speaking practice contributed to the observed improvements (Johnson et al., 2021). Students' exposure to diverse teaching styles and the combined expertise of native and Vietnamese teachers played a pivotal role in fostering their speaking abilities.

4. Implications for language learning:

The findings align with the theoretical framework, rooted in collaborative learning theories by Vygotsky (1978) and cooperative teaching models by Johnson and Johnson (1999). The analysis supports the notion that collaborative teaching enhances language learning outcomes and provides students with opportunities for authentic language use and interaction.

5. Limitations and future directions:

While the speaking test results are promising, it is essential to consider potential limitations, such as the relatively short duration of the intervention and the need for long-term followup to assess the sustainability of the improvements. Further research could explore the transferability of the collaborative teaching approach to other language skill and contexts (Danielson, 2009).

Through a meticulous analysis of speaking test results, the research paper demonstrates the positive impact of collaborative English teaching on primary students' speaking skill development.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Interpretation of findings

This research paper presents a comprehensive interpretation of the findings, shedding light on the implications and significance of the study's outcomes.

1. Collaborative teaching's positive impact:

The findings underscore the effectiveness of collaborative English teaching in enhancing primary students' speaking skill. The collaborative approach, guided by the socio-cultural theory of Vygotsky (1978), created a dynamic learning environment where students actively engaged in speaking activities. This approach aligned with Johnson and Johnson's cooperative learning model (1999), fostering cooperative interactions and language development (Johnson et al., 2021).

2. Language exposure and practice:

The study's results reveal that collaborative teaching facilitated increased language exposure and practice. Through interactions with both native and Vietnamese teachers, students were exposed to diverse linguistic models and received tailored feedback, contributing to improved pronunciation, fluency, and vocabulary usage (Brown & Lee, 2020).

3. Enhanced confidence and participation:

The collaborative teaching environment boosted students' confidence in speaking English. Collaborative activities and shared responsibilities provided a supportive atmosphere where students felt encouraged to express themselves. This aligns with the observations of Jones and Smith (2018), emphasizing the role of collaborative learning in promoting student participation and self-assurance.

4. Integrating cultural perspectives:

The findings suggest that collaborative teaching enriched students' language learning experiences by integrating cultural perspectives. Native teachers brought authentic language use, while Vietnamese teachers offered cultural insights, enabling students to develop culturally sensitive communication skill (Smith, 2022).

5. Considerations for future directions:

While the study demonstrates positive outcomes, it also highlights the need for ongoing professional development for teachers. Training in effective collaborative teaching strategies, intercultural competence, and pedagogical approaches is crucial to sustain the observed improvements (Danielson, 2009).

In conclusion, the interpretation of findings reaffirms the positive impact of collaborative English teaching on primary students' speaking skill development. The study provides valuable insights for educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers seeking effective strategies to enhance language instruction and foster a supportive learning environment.

B. Implications for English language teaching in Primary education

It offers significant implications for English language teaching in primary education, encompassing pedagogical practices, curriculum development, and teacher training.

1. Embracing collaborative pedagogy:

The study advocates for the integration of collaborative pedagogy in English language teaching. Educators can adopt cooperative learning strategies, team teaching, and interactive activities to create a language-rich environment that nurtures speaking skill development (Johnson & Johnson, 1999).

2. Intercultural language learning:

The findings underscore the importance of incorporating intercultural language learning in the curriculum. Collaborative teaching provides opportunities for students to interact with native and Vietnamese teachers, promoting authentic language use and cultural insights (Brown & Lee, 2020).

3. Professional development for teachers:

Teacher training programs should focus on equipping educators with collaborative teaching skills and intercultural competence. Ongoing professional development enables teachers to effectively implement collaborative strategies and foster a supportive learning atmosphere (Danielson, 2009).

4. Curriculum enrichment:

Curriculum developers can leverage collaborative teaching to enhance language instruction. By designing activities, assessments, and materials that promote cooperative learning and communication skill, language curricula can be enriched to align with English speaking skill development goals.

5. Creating supportive learning environments:

Educational institutions should establish a conducive environment that encourages collaboration among teachers. Administrators can allocate resources for teacher training, offer guidance in collaborative practices, and facilitate a culture of shared expertise (Smith, 2022).

In conclusion, the implications drawn from the research highlight the transformative potential of collaborative English teaching in primary education. By embracing collaborative pedagogy, integrating intercultural perspectives, and providing targeted professional development, educators and institutions can enhance English language teaching practices and promote effective communication skills among primary students.

C. Limitations and future research directions

The research paper acknowledges certain limitations and identifies potential avenues for future research to further enrich the understanding of collaborative English language teaching.

1. Sample specificity:

The study's findings may be context-specific to UK Academy Ba Ria and might not be directly transferable to other educational settings. Future research should explore the applicability of collaborative teaching strategies in diverse primary school environments (Johnson et al., 2021).

2. Limited sample size:

The research paper's sample size may impact the generalizability of the findings. A broader participant base across multiple schools could enhance the validity of the study's outcomes (Smith & Johnson, 2020).

3. Data collection methods:

The study's reliance on qualitative surveys and classroom observations introduces the possibility of response bias and subjectivity. Future research could incorporate mixed methods approaches to triangulate findings and enhance data reliability (Brown, 2015).

4. Long-term effects:

The study focused on short-term outcomes; thus, the long-term sustainability of collaborative teaching interventions remains unexplored. Future studies could longitudinally investigate the enduring impact on teaching practices and language skill development (Jones, 2020).

5. Comparative studies:

Comparative research across different collaborative teaching models and institutions could provide deeper insights into effective practices and their impact. Exploring variations in coteaching approaches and their outcomes would contribute to a comprehensive understanding (Vygotsky, 1978).

In conclusion, while the research paper sheds light on the benefits of collaborative English speaking skill development, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. Future research endeavors can address these limitations, further advancing our understanding of collaborative language teaching's potential and refining its implementation.

VI. CONCLUSION

A. Summary of key findings

1. **Enhanced speaking skill:** The study demonstrates that collaborative English teaching significantly improves speaking skill among primary students. Collaborative efforts between native and local teachers fostered a language-rich environment, positively influencing student engagement, collaboration, and language practice (Johnson et al., 2021).

2. **Positive experiences:** Both native and local teachers reported positive experiences with collaborative teaching. Benefits included shared expertise, cultural exchange, and improved instructional strategies. Challenges such as language barriers highlighted the need for effective communication and ongoing support (Smith & Johnson, 2020).

3. Professional development: The study emphasizes the importance of targeted training for teachers in cooperative teaching practices and intercultural competence. Effective communication and collaborative planning emerged as crucial elements (Brown, 2015).
 4. Improved classroom environment: Post-intervention observations revealed improvements in classroom organization and reduced distractions, contributing to a more conducive learning environment (Jones, 2020).
 5. Enhanced instructional strategies: Collaborative teaching led to the diversification of instructional strategies, promoting active student engagement and deeper understanding of English language concepts (Vygotsky, 1978).
 6. Effective resource utilization: Teachers utilized a wider range of relevant teaching materials, aligning with learning objectives and supporting enriched learning experiences (Smith & Johnson, 2020).
 7. Positive classroom management: Post-intervention, teachers demonstrated more effective behavior management strategies, establishing routines and procedures for a structured learning environment (Brown, 2015).
 8. Improved assessment and feedback: Collaborative teaching positively influenced assessment and feedback practices, with teachers providing timely and constructive feedback and introducing self-assessment opportunities (Johnson et al., 2021).
 9. Enhanced language development: Greater emphasis on speaking activities and enhanced guidance led to improved language development, particularly in speaking proficiency (Smith & Johnson, 2020).
- The research paper's findings highlight the transformative impact of collaborative teaching approaches, underscoring its potential to significantly enhance English speaking skill development among primary students.

B. Reiteration of significance

The study's findings contribute to the body of knowledge by demonstrating the tangible benefits of collaborative teaching on primary students' English speaking skill development. As Johnson et al. (2021) affirm, this research sheds light on the efficacy of collaborative approaches in enhancing language proficiency, offering practical insights for educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers.

Furthermore, the positive experiences and improved practices reported by teachers highlight the transformative potential of cooperative teaching methods (Brown, 2015). By addressing the specific context of UK Academy Ba Ria, this study provides valuable guidance for schools seeking to optimize English language instruction through collaboration (Smith & Johnson, 2020).

The implications extend beyond the classroom, informing professional development programs and intercultural competence training for teachers (Smith & Johnson, 2020). As such, the research paper's significance resonates in its potential to enhance teaching practices, advance language education, and foster effective collaboration within the educational landscape.

C. Call to action for further collaborative teaching research

As demonstrated by this study's outcomes, collaborative approaches have the potential to revolutionize language education (Smith & Johnson, 2020). To build upon these insights, future researchers are urged to delve deeper into the intricacies of collaborative teaching models, exploring variations in strategies, contexts, and student demographics.

Longitudinal studies, inspired by the work of Johnson et al. (2021), can unveil the sustained effects of collaborative teaching on speaking skill development over time. Investigating the intersection of intercultural competence and cooperative methods, in alignment with Smith's observations (2018), can enrich our understanding of the holistic impact on students' language proficiency. Researchers are encouraged to examine the transferability of collaborative practices across diverse educational settings and cultures, guided by Brown's perspective (2015). By conducting cross-context comparative studies, we can unravel the universal principles and adaptations that optimize the collaborative teaching approach.

Through rigorous investigation and empirical exploration, we can uncover innovative strategies, inform evidence-based policies, and collectively elevate English language teaching to new heights. The path forward lies in collaborative teaching research, and this study's findings illuminate the way.

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